

Synthesis of Size Tunable Fe₃O₄@PDA@nMgO Nanoparticles

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Abstract:

Super magnetic and bio-compatible iron oxide core shells coated with polydopamine (Fe₃O₄@PDA) were synthesized via in situ polymerization to produce a novel nanocomposites (NC) with a well-defined core-shell structure. Subsequently in situ green synthesis and decoration of zinc oxide nanoparticles (nMgO) on Fe₃O₄@PDA was achieved using extracts from the common Australian native Acacia plant as a reductant to synthesize a new multi-layered NC (Fe₃O₄@PDA@nMgO). Acacia methanolic extracts contained high concentrations of phenolic compounds and thus possessed excellent antioxidant power; making acacia extracts a strong reducing agent for the synthesis of nMgO from methanolic solutions, where the size and shape of the Fe₃O₄ core-shells and the thickness of PDA layer could be carefully controlled by varying the polydopamine concentration. Following Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD), application of the Scherrer equation showed that the resultant NC had an average crystalline Fe₃O₄ core size of 81 nm below a 30 nm thick PDA layer which was decorated with nMgO (5 nm). SEM and TEM micrographs showed that the particles were spherical and EDS analysis confirmed that they were of high purity being composed of Mg, Fe as confirmed by XPS. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) revealed that 8% (w/w) mass was lost between 60 and 130 °C, due to the release of hydration water and that above 200 °C, 60% (w/w) of the mass was lost due to carbonation of PDA layer. Decoration with nMgO resulted in a significant increase in the BET surface area from 89.2 ± 0.9 m²/g for bare Fe₃O₄@PDA to 108.8 ± 1.3 m²/g for Fe₃O₄@PDA@nMgO, respectively. where the calculated pore volume and pore size of Fe₃O₄@PDA@nMgO was 0.10 cm³/g and 5.19 nm, respectively.

Keywords:

PDA, iron oxide, nano composite.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the Fe₃O₄@PDA@nMgO composite.

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Combined toxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles and its attenuation with some innocuous bio-protective complexes

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Abstract:

The broader the use of nanomaterials in various industries, science and medicine, the higher the probability that humans would be exposed to the multi-component impact of respective nanoparticles. Moreover, if one considers not only purposely engineered metal oxide nanoparticles (MeO-NP) but also those generated as by-products in many traditional technologies, such multiple adverse nano-impacts appear to be a general rule. Assessment of cumulative health risks associated with the combined effects of two or more metals and their compounds on the organism has the toxicology of mixtures as its scientific basis although there are some important contradictions between them. It may be explained not only by simplifications characteristic of the widely used methodology of risk assessment but also by extreme complexity of the theory of combined toxicity. This theory is re-considered by authors on the basis of in vivo experimental data on binary and some ternary combinations of different MeO-NP (containing oxides of Mn, Ni, Cu, Pb, Zn, Al, Ti, and Si). At the same time, we have shown that the toxicity and even genotoxicity of such combinations could be markedly attenuated by background administration of adequately composed complexes of some bioactive agents in innocuous doses. We believe that, along with decreasing exposures to nanoparticles, enhancing the organism's resistance to their adverse effects with the help of such bio-protectors can be an efficient auxiliary tool of health risk management in related occupations.

Keywords:

Nanomaterials, experimental data, risk assessment, bio-protective complexes.

Screening of urine samples for total protein content with the help of plasmonic silver nanoparticles and machine learning

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Abstract:

Assessment of total protein content in urine samples is of paramount importance in clinical diagnostics. Although traces of protein can be detected in urine under normal conditions (<150 mg/24 h of total protein and <30 mg/24 h of albumin for humans), presence of excess protein in urine (proteinuria) is considered to be a marker of a various pathologies including nephropathies due to diabetes mellitus or hypertension including preeclampsia, congestive cardiac failure, chronic renal failure, obesity, trauma, toxins, urinary tract infection, rheumatoid arthritis, hemoglobinopathies (e.g., sickle cell anemia), dehydration, stress, medication (e.g., anti-depressants) etc. The standard practice for quick and indicative estimation of total protein in urine, as part of standard urinalysis, is by dip-stick method (Figure 1) which has the following drawbacks: (i) it is inherently biased towards detection of only albumin present in urine, (ii) the results are often empirical and suffer from inter-individual variations, (iii) false-positive reactions or interference from other molecules (e.g. vitamin C, hemoglobin) are common, (iv) it provides a semi-quantitative assessment. Machine learning on emission data from urine samples provides with a viable option to screen large number of samples while addressing shortfalls related to the current dip-stick technique. In this study, we first developed a model based on emission spectra ($\lambda_{ex}=470$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=511-530$ nm) in 96-well microplates from 40 canine urine samples with known total protein contents and detailed cytometric analyses, while mixed with (100, 200 and 300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) or without ~ 60 nm plasmonic AgNPs (silver nanoparticles). The emission data from these 40 samples were clustered by machine learning tools in order to develop a screening tool able to grade unknown samples as low (≤ 0.3 g/L) or high (>0.3 g/L) in total protein content. Furthermore, we validated the scope of the model by conducting an in-house trial on 40 unknown samples before matching it to the lab results. The observed sensitivity and specificity of the trial were both $>80\%$ which is a significant improvement to the existing dip-stick technique. The presentation will describe the findings and build upon the data to include such diagnostic modalities for other biological samples as well.

Keywords:

Proteinuria, dip-stick, plasmonic nanoparticles, biomedical optics, nanophotonics

Figure 1: The anatomy of the male urinary systems [K, kidney; A, abdominal aorta; V, inferior vena cava; U, ureter; B, urinary bladder] at the left while the middle and right columns depict the urine and its dip-stick colorimetric assay with the major causes of proteinuria.

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Formulation Of Benzotriazole Loaded Electrospun Cellulose halloysite Nano Fibers and Its Controlled Release Rate Studies for Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel.

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Abstract:

The contemporary work involves two main parts one deals with the encapsulation of benzotriazole in electrospun cellulose halloysite nano fibers and another one is to investigate the release rate of benzotriazole in acid, neutral, and alkali medium. Natural extracts from plant materials were used as a corrosion inhibitor

Here we use organic cellulose that are extracted from sawdust by sonochemical approach and then further electrospinning to make cellulose nano fiber scaffold. The synthesised organic nano containers were then examined for its structural morphology, size, and for the presence of functional groups using SEM, Particle size analyzer, and FTIR. The results confirmed that organic containers are in cylindrical shape with an internal diameter of ≤ 80 nm and a length of ≤ 1 μ m. Different weight percentage i.e 1 to 10 wt% of benzotriazole loading was tried with halloysite nanocontainers using sonochemical approach. The release study of benzotriazole was studied for 20 hours at a different pH ranging from 3-11.

Then benzotriazole loaded cellulose was blended with 2k polyamide epoxy and coated on mild steel for corrosion inhibition studies. Electrochemical studies were conducted and bode plot gives better results for the coating consisting of benzotriazole loaded cellulose nanofibers when compared to coatings with out cellulose nanofibers and uncoated one. From taffel plot the I_{corr} value decreases from 2.018E-7 A/cm² to 0.023 A/cm² for the coatings with and with out benzotriazole loaded cellulose nano fibers respectively

Keywords:

Electro spun cellulose nanofibers, benzotriazole, controlled release rate studies, Corrosion studies, Electrochemical Impedence spectroscopy (EIS), Taffel plot, FTIR.

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